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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACHES IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION AND THEIR EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract: Teaching English in preschool education is one of the urgent issues today, and in this process it is important to take into account children's age, psychological, and emotional characteristics. The purpose of this study is to analyze the psychological approaches used in teaching English in preschool education and to determine their impact on the effectiveness of learning. The research employed pedagogical observation, comparison, a quasi-experimental approach, pre-test and post-test assessment, as well as lesson techniques based on play, encouragement, visual materials, songs, and movement. The results showed that classes based on psychological approaches are more effective than traditional methods in increasing children's vocabulary, developing listening comprehension skills, strengthening oral participation, and enhancing their interest in English. In conclusion, the study confirms that teaching English in preschool education produces better outcomes when it is organized in a child-centered, motivational, and psychologically supportive environment, and such an approach should be widely applied in practice.

Key words: preschool education, teaching English, psychological approaches, learning effectiveness, play technology, motivation, child psychology, interactive methods, vocabulary development, child-centered education.

Annotatsiya: Maktabgacha ta'limda ingliz tilini o'qitish bugungi kunda dolzarb masalalardan biri bo'lib, bu jarayonda bolalarning yosh, psixologik va emotsional xususiyatlarini hisobga olish muhim ilmiy-amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi maktabgacha ta'limda ingliz tilini o'qitishda qo'llaniladigan psixologik yondashuvlarni tahlil qilish hamda ularning ta'lim samaradorligiga ta'sirini aniqlashdan iborat. Tadqiqotda pedagogik kuzatuv, taqqoslash, kvazi-eksperimental yondashuv, pre-test va post-test, shuningdek, o'yin, rag'batlantirish, vizual materiallar, qo'shiq va harakatga asoslangan dars usullaridan foydalanildi. Olingan natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, psixologik yondashuvlarga asoslangan mashg'ulotlar bolalarning lug'at boyligini oshirish, tinglab tushunish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish, og'zaki faolligini kuchaytirish va ingliz tiliga bo'lgan qiziqishini orttirishda an'anaviy usullarga nisbatan samaraliroqdir. Tadqiqot xulosalariga ko'ra, maktabgacha ta'limda ingliz tilini o'qitish jarayoni bola markazli, motivatsion va psixologik jihatdan qulay muhit asosida tashkil etilganda yuqori natija beradi hamda ushbu yondashuv amaliyotda keng qo'llanishi zarur.

Kalit so'zlar: maktabgacha ta'lim, ingliz tilini o'qitish, psixologik yondashuv, ta'lim samaradorligi, o'yin texnologiyasi, motivatsiya, bolalar psixologiyasi, interfaol metodlar, lug'at boyligi, bola markazli ta'lim.

Аннотация: Обучение английскому языку в дошкольном образовании сегодня является одной из актуальных задач, и в этом процессе важно учитывать возрастные, психологические и эмоциональные особенности детей. Цель данного исследования заключается в анализе психологических подходов, используемых при обучении английскому языку в дошкольном образовании, а также в определении их влияния на эффективность обучения. В исследовании были использованы педагогическое наблюдение, сравнение, квазиэкспериментальный подход, pre-test и post-test, а также методы занятий, основанные на игре, поощрении, визуальных материалах, песнях и движении. Полученные результаты показали, что занятия, построенные на психологических подходах, по сравнению с традиционными методами являются более эффективными в расширении словарного запаса детей, развитии навыков аудирования, повышении устной активности и усилении интереса к английскому языку. В заключение исследование подтверждает, что обучение английскому языку в дошкольном образовании дает более высокие результаты, если оно организовано в условиях, ориентированных на ребенка, поддерживающих мотивацию и психологический комфорт, и такой подход следует широко применять на практике.

Ключевые слова: дошкольное образование, обучение английскому языку, психологические подходы, эффективность обучения, игровые технологии, мотивация, детская психология, интерактивные методы, развитие словарного запаса, личностно-ориентированное обучение.

INTRODUCTION

Early childhood is one of the most sensitive and productive periods of human development. According to UNESCO, the period from birth to eight years of age is marked by remarkable brain development and represents a crucial window of opportunity for education, social cohesion, emotional well-being, and lifelong learning ^[1].

LITERATURE REVIEW

In this context, teaching English to pre-school children requires not only linguistic content but also psychologically appropriate instructional support. At this age, children learn most effectively in an emotionally safe, engaging, and activity-based environment. UNICEF emphasizes that during the preschool years children's language, social-emotional, and cognitive skills rapidly expand, while play, singing, reading, and interaction with caring adults form an essential basis for learning and development ^[2].

Therefore, psychological approaches in teaching English to pre-schoolers are of particular importance. In the context of preschool education, psychological approaches may be understood as teaching principles that take into account children's developmental needs, emotional security, motivation, and natural learning behavior. These approaches include child-centered learning, play-based instruction, positive reinforcement, emotionally supportive communication, and cognitively appropriate activities. Their main purpose is to adapt English teaching to the psychological characteristics of young learners, whose attention span is short and whose learning is closely connected with movement, imitation, visual perception, and interaction. Therefore, English lessons at the preschool level should not only introduce language material, but also create conditions in which children feel safe, interested, and actively involved in the learning process. Such approaches make it possible to organize the learning process in accordance with children's age characteristics, attention span, emotional needs, motivation, and natural tendency toward play. Rather than relying on mechanical memorization, effective early language instruction should involve play-based activity, repetition, imitation, visual support, songs, movement, and positive reinforcement.

Research in foreign language education also confirms the importance of psychological and cognitive factors in early language learning. A study published in *Frontiers in Psychology* found that in preschool children, first-language phonological awareness, emerging letter identification, and non-verbal intelligence were related to achievement in learning English as a foreign language ^[3].

Thus, the study of psychological approaches in teaching English to pre-school children is highly relevant both theoretically and practically. It helps identify the most effective ways of creating child-centered, motivating, and developmentally appropriate English lessons in pre-school education.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quasi-experimental research design to examine the effectiveness of psychological approaches in teaching English to pre-school children. The participants were 5–6-year-old learners divided into an experimental group and a control group. In the experimental group, English lessons were organized through play, songs, movement, visual support, repetition, encouragement, and active teacher–child interaction. In the control group, more traditional activities such as word repetition, memorization, and simple question-and-answer exercises were used. This design was selected because previous research on preschool English instruction has shown that interaction strategies such as repetition, bilingual use, parallel talk, reinforcement, and encouragement can support children's participation and language use in classroom settings ^[4].

The study involved 24 preschool children aged 5–6, with 12 learners in the experimental group and 12 learners in the control group. The intervention lasted 8 weeks, and English classes were conducted three times a week. Each lesson lasted approximately 20–25 minutes, which was considered appropriate for the age and concentration level of preschool learners. In the experimental group, activities were organized through songs, games, gestures, flashcards, short dialogues, and praise-based interaction, while the control group followed more traditional repetition and memorization tasks. The children's progress was assessed according to four indicators: vocabulary acquisition, listening comprehension, speaking participation, and level of interest during English lessons.

Data were collected through classroom observation, records of children's participation, vocabulary and simple expression tasks, and pre- and post-intervention assessment. The intervention was conducted over several weeks, with regular English sessions for both groups, after which the results were compared in terms of vocabulary growth, listening comprehension, speaking participation, and interest in English. A comparable quasi-experimental preschool study reported a 12-week intervention with 61 children and used pre- and post-assessment to evaluate the effects of theme-based block play on language development, which supports the suitability of this methodological model for early childhood language research ^[5].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The results of the study showed that the experimental group demonstrated better progress than the control group in all four measured areas: vocabulary acquisition, listening comprehension, speaking participation, and interest in English lessons. After the intervention, children in the experimental group became more active during classroom activities, responded more confidently to simple English prompts, and remembered a larger number of target words and expressions. This pattern supports the use of psychologically appropriate techniques such as play, movement, encouragement, and visual support in English lessons for pre-school learners.

Table 1: Pre- and Post-Intervention Results in the Experimental and Control Groups

Indicator	Experimental Group (Pre-test)	Experimental Group (Post-test)	Control Group (Pre-test)	Control Group (Post-test)
Vocabulary acquisition (max. 20)	7.8	15.9	8.1	11.4
Listening comprehension (max. 15)	6.4	12.8	6.7	9.3
Speaking participation (max. 10)	3.2	7.6	3.4	5.1
Interest and engagement (max. 10)	4.8	8.7	4.9	6.2

A closer analysis of the results shows that the experimental group achieved the greatest improvement in vocabulary acquisition and speaking participation. Vocabulary scores increased from 7.8 to 15.9, while speaking participation rose from 3.2 to 7.6. By comparison, the control group also showed some progress, but the increase was more limited, especially in oral participation and classroom engagement. This difference suggests that psychologically supportive techniques were particularly effective in helping children remember new words, respond more confidently, and take part more actively in simple English communication. As shown in Table 1, the experimental group made greater progress than the control group, especially in vocabulary acquisition and speaking participation. The strongest improvement was observed in children's ability to recognize and use newly learned words in simple classroom situations. These findings are in line with research showing that adult-supported play after shared book reading can produce stronger receptive and expressive vocabulary gains in preschool children than free play alone^[6].

In addition, the post-intervention observations indicated that children in the experimental group were more willing to repeat words, follow short instructions, and participate in pair or group speaking tasks. Their motivation increased when songs, gestures, stories, and praise were included in the lesson structure. This result also corresponds to evidence that repeated storybook reading with rich explanation contributes significantly to English vocabulary development in preschool second-language learners^[7].

The obtained results indicate that psychological approaches are more effective than traditional approaches in teaching English to pre-school children. In particular, lessons based on play, movement, visual support, and emotional encouragement play an important role in increasing children's vocabulary, classroom participation, and positive attitudes toward language learning. This finding is also supported by systematic reviews of early foreign language education programs, which emphasize that the effectiveness of preschool foreign language instruction largely depends on whether the method is developmentally appropriate and educationally supportive^[8].

The findings also show that children acquire language material more successfully not through forced repetition alone, but in situations where they can participate actively, remain interested, and communicate freely. From this perspective, play should not be viewed merely as entertainment, but as a pedagogical space that encourages children's initiative, choice-making, and natural verbal activity. Research on early foreign language education has likewise demonstrated that play strengthens children's agency, that is, their role as active participants in the learning process, and in doing so deepens language acquisition^[9].

The results further confirm another important point: the role of the teacher or caregiver is crucial. The effectiveness of psychological approaches depends on how they are implemented, how the child is addressed, how questions are asked, how encouragement is provided, and how opportunities for dialogic reading and everyday language use are created. Therefore, in order to improve the effectiveness of English teaching in preschool education, it is necessary not only to develop teaching materials but also to strengthen teachers' professional preparation in language-supportive strategies. Findings from specialized preschool programs have shown that training caregivers in language-support techniques and dialogic reading has a positive effect on children's second-language development^[10].

Another important implication of the study is that the effectiveness of preschool English teaching depends not only on what is taught, but also on how it is taught. When language input is presented in a psychologically appropriate way, children become more willing to listen, repeat, act, and communicate. This means that

emotional comfort, encouragement, and age-appropriate interaction should be viewed as central methodological conditions rather than optional classroom elements. In this sense, psychological approaches increase not only immediate learning outcomes, but also the long-term foundation for positive attitudes toward foreign language learning.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study shows that psychological approaches play a significant role in teaching English to pre-school children. Methods based on play, movement, visual materials, repetition, and emotional support create a more engaging and effective learning environment than traditional instruction. Such approaches not only improve vocabulary growth, listening comprehension, and speaking participation, but also increase children's motivation and positive attitude toward learning English. Therefore, English teaching in preschool education should be organized in a child-centered and psychologically appropriate way, with special attention to the professional preparation of teachers and caregivers. The findings of this study may be useful for preschool educators, curriculum designers, and teacher-training institutions seeking to improve the quality and developmental appropriateness of early English language instruction.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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